

Optimal Power Flow Solutions Using Hybrid Recursive Static Var Compensator–Capacitor–Neural Controller for Enhanced Grid Stability

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Abstract

Optimal power flow solutions are crucial for improved power system efficiency, reliability, and sustainability. Efficient supply of electricity consists of sufficient generation, strong power transfer capability, and reliable power utilization. We proposed and analyzed the performance of a hybrid recursive Static Var Compensator (SVC)–Capacitor–Neural Controller (SCNRC) system on a power system of nine 11kV feeders based on IEEE requirements. The methodology integrates the continuous compensation of SVC, governed by an adaptive Recursive Least Squares (RLS) gain and a Neural Network (NN) correction term, with discrete bulk compensation provided by switched-capacitor banks operating under hysteresis and dwell-time constraints. Simulations utilizing the integrated control law were conducted in the Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP) and MATLAB/Simulink to evaluate the system against baseline compensation strategies using performance index J. The SCNRC system achieved a 22% reduction in system power losses, an 82% decrease in voltage deviation, and a 40% improvement. The method is also applied to the IEEE 14-bus system, reducing the base-case power loss from 0.18 p.u. to 0.07 p.u., representing a 61.11% improvement. Similarly, voltage deviation is reduced from 0.10 p.u. to 0.01 p.u. The findings provide a robust and scalable solution for modern power grid management.

Keywords: Hybridization compensation, Static var compensator, Capacitor banks, Recursive least square, Discrete compensation, Neural network.

1.0 Introduction

In power systems, both Static Var Compensators (SVCs) and capacitor banks provide reactive power compensation and voltage support. In terms of differences, SVCs provide dynamic reactive power compensation, whereas capacitor banks provide fixed or stepwise compensation. SVCs have a faster response time than capacitor banks. SVCs are more flexible than capacitor banks [1]. The SVC is seen as a shunt device; its structural arrangement allows the capacitors to generate reactive power and inductors, also referred to as reactors, to absorb it when connected to alternating-current power mains [2]. FACTS devices are effective for compensating reactive power and have become the most efficient means of enhancing the efficiency of the transmission network [3]. Operation of a power system closer to its loadability limit is always dictated by deregulated electricity markets. Hence, voltage instability is a consequence in most cases, especially if no corrective measures are taken to ensure system security and improve power quality [4].

Nonlinear loads generate harmonic currents, thereby increasing the inductive reactance and reducing the capacitive reactance of the system [5]. In [6], a robust power system is defined as one that maintains acceptable voltages at various buses under normal operating conditions and after disturbances. The SVC controls and manages reactive power to improve voltage profile and stability margins [1]. Increasing demand under power supply inadequacy will always push the system to its peak capacity, tending to violate the grid voltage rule [7]. Sufficient study of load flow is essential because it is cardinal to the successful planning and maintenance of the power system, provided the system is stable [8]. Voltage instability in the power system arises from heavily loaded transmission lines and insufficient reactive power availability [9]. New control methods are necessary to sustain the grid system [10].

Neural networks in power systems provide load forecasting, state estimation, optimal power flow, fault diagnosis, voltage stability assessment, and energy management systems. These are possible because neural networks can handle complexities, make real-time decisions, and adapt. A hybrid solution is still the answer to the problem of system instability. A solution that will advance the power system toward optimal performance, cost-effectiveness, and greater flexibility is urgently needed if homes, industries, and commercial activities must thrive. The UST injection substation is characterized by voltage and load variation issues. As a matter of concern, this research aims to model the system to enable optimal power flow. The objectives of this paper are to:

- i. model the power system with SVCs to get its contribution in the power system
- ii. model the power system with capacitor banks to get its contribution
- iii. simulate the integrated control of SVCs and capacitor banks to ascertain their contribution
- iv. simulate the integrated control of SVCs, neural networks, and capacitor banks for optimal load flow and enhanced grid stability.
- v. validate results using the IEEE 14 bus system.

2.0 Methodology

The methodology used here to address a power system characterized by voltage instability and power loss problems is based on a hybrid recursive Static Var Compensator (SVC)–Capacitor–Neural Controller (SCNRC) system. A prototype power system, which was upgraded and modeled in accordance with UST 2 X 15 MVA, 33/11 kV Injection Substation located at the Rivers State University, Nigeria, has load uncertainties and voltage instability problems. The power system comprises 9 of 11kV feeders, as depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Single-Line Diagram of the Power System

Feeders 1, 2, and 3 are connected to the first transformer (T1A). Feeders 4, 5, and 6 are connected to the second transformer (T2A) while feeders 7, 8, and 9 are connected to the third transformer (T3A). Each transformer is rated at 15 MVA and 12 MW,

respectively, and must be curtailed to 10MW for the safe operation of all power equipment within the system. As a system with voltage and demand issues, corrective measures are required to address all concerns and attain steady-state stability.

2.1 Data Collection

Primary and secondary data with respect to power substations, power transformers and lines were available from the Transmission Company of Nigeria (TCN), Port Harcourt Region, and UST injection substation for the purpose of establishing the fact that a power system can be more stable and reliable with the inclusion of capacitor banks and static var compensators. The Electrical Transient Analyzer Program (ETAP) software was so comprehensive, with some built-in parameters for this purpose. For the sake of novelty, hybridization of a static var compensator, a neural network and capacitors was implemented in MATLAB/Simulink. The procedure followed the sequence of power system modeling as indicated below using ETAP and MATLAB software applications.

2.2 Modeling of Static Var Compensators

The SVC is modeled as a controllable reactive power device whose output depends on the bus voltage and its effective susceptance. This relationship enables dynamic voltage regulation by adjusting the firing angle of thyristors, making it a critical component in maintaining system stability.

$$Q_{SVC} = V_i^2 \times B_{SVC}(\alpha) \quad (1)$$

where Q_{SVC} is reactive power output, V_i is bus voltage, and $B_{SVC}(\alpha)$ is susceptance.

The susceptance of the SVC varies with the firing angle, providing a nonlinear control mechanism that allows continuous adjustment of reactive power. This formulation captures the physical behavior of the SVC and directly links control action to system response.

$$B_{SVC}(\alpha) = B_C - \frac{1}{\pi X_L} (2\alpha - \sin 2\alpha) \quad (2)$$

where B_C is capacitive susceptance, X_L is inductive reactance, and α is firing angle.

2.3 Modeling of Capacitor Banks

Capacitor banks are modeled as discrete reactive power sources that can be switched on or off depending on system requirements. This discrete representation reflects practical implementation in power systems, where capacitor units are operated in steps rather than continuously.

$$Q_{CAP} = \sum_{k=1}^M u_k Q_k \quad (3)$$

where Q_{CAP} is total reactive power, u_k is switching state, Q_k is unit rating, and M is number of units.

$$\text{Active power, } P_i = \sum_{j=1}^N V_i V_j (G_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij}) \quad (4)$$

where P_i is the active power at bus i , V_i is the voltage magnitude at bus i , G_{ij} and B_{ij} are the conductance and susceptance between buses i and j , and θ_{ij} is the phase angle difference between buses i and j .

$$\text{Reactive power, } Q_i = \sum_{j=1}^N V_i V_j (B_{ij} \cos \theta_{ij} - G_{ij} \sin \theta_{ij}) \quad (5)$$

where Q_i is the reactive power at bus i .

The objective function to minimize is the total system power loss:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (G_{ij} \Delta P_{ij} + B_{ij} \Delta Q_{ij}) \quad (6)$$

where ΔP_{ij} and ΔQ_{ij} represent the changes in active and reactive power due to system adjustments.

The constraints are as follows

- Voltage limits: $V_{min} \leq V_i \leq V_{max}$
- Generator limits: $P_i^{min} \leq P_i \leq P_i^{max}$
- Line flow limits: $S_{ij}^{max} \leq S_{ij} \leq S_{ij}^{max}$

where S_{ij} is the flow between buses i and j .

The performance index J combines multiple objectives such as minimizing power losses, voltage deviations, and capacitor switching penalties. The weights w_1 , w_2 , and w_3 determine the relative importance of each objective. These weights are empirically chosen based on the system's operational priorities. A typical set of weights could be $w_1 = 0.5$, $w_2 = 0.3$, and $w_3 = 0.2$, but these can be adjusted to reflect system-specific needs.

The Recursive Least Squares (RLS) method is used to adaptively tune the SVC gain, while the Neural Network (NN) correction term dynamically adjusts the capacitor bank sizing for optimal reactive power compensation.

Figure 2: Power System with SVCs (Simulated)

Figure 3: Power System with Capacitor Banks (Simulated)

Figure 4: Power System with SVCs and Capacitor Banks (Simulated)

2.4 Integrated Control (SVC + NN + Capacitor)

The recursive hybrid controller dynamically adjusts Q_t^{svc} through adaptive gain K_t and nonlinear neural term $\mathcal{N}(x_t; \Theta_t)$, ensuring real-time voltage stability and improved reactive power compensation accuracy using Equation (7):

$$Q_t^{\text{tot}} = Q_t^{\text{svc}} + Q_t^{\text{cap}} = K_t e_t + \mathcal{N}(x_t; \Theta_t) + Q_t^{\text{cap}} \quad (7)$$

where x_t is the neural network input vector, typically $x_t = [V_t, e_t, Q_{t-1}^{\text{svc}}]$.

The recursive least squares (RLS) algorithm continuously updates the controller gain K_t using past errors and system responses using Equation (8):

$$K_{t+1} = K_t + P_t \phi_t \frac{(y_t - \phi_t^T K_t)}{\lambda + \phi_t^T P_t \phi_t} \quad (8)$$

$$P_{t+1} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left(P_t - \frac{P_t \phi_t \phi_t^T P_t}{\lambda + \phi_t^T P_t \phi_t} \right) \quad (9)$$

where ϕ_t is the regressor (e.g., e_t), y_t is the observation, P_t is the covariance matrix, and $0 < \lambda \leq 1$ is the forgetting factor.

The adaptive learning process allows the network to capture nonlinear system behaviors, complementing the RLS linear model using Equation (10):

$$\Theta_{t+1} = \Theta_t - \eta \nabla_{\Theta} \mathcal{L}_t(\Theta_t) \quad (10)$$

where the instantaneous loss function is defined in Equation (11):

$$\mathcal{L}_t(\Theta) = \frac{1}{2} \| e_{t+1} \|^2 \approx \frac{1}{2} \| V_{\text{ref}} - V_{t+1}(\Theta) \|^2 \quad (11)$$

where η is the neural learning rate.

Equation (12) models the discrete switching control of capacitor banks subject to hysteresis and dwell-time constraints.

$$s_{i,t+1} = \begin{cases} s_{i,t} + 1, & \text{if } V_{i,t} < V_{\text{ref}} - h \text{ and } \tau_{i,t} \geq T_{\text{dwell}}, \\ s_{i,t} - 1, & \text{if } V_{i,t} > V_{\text{ref}} + h \text{ and } \tau_{i,t} \geq T_{\text{dwell}}, \\ s_{i,t}, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

The capacitor injection level is calculated using Equation (13):

$$Q_{i,t}^{\text{cap}} = s_{i,t} \Delta Q_{\text{cap}} \quad (13)$$

where $\tau_{i,t}$ is the time since the last switching event and h is the hysteresis band.

The performance index combines power loss, voltage deviation, and switching penalties into a unified evaluation metric using Equation (14):

$$J = w_1 P_{\text{loss}} + w_2 \sum_i |V_i - V_{\text{ref}}| + w_3 \sum_i \mathbb{1}\{\text{switch}_i\} \quad (14)$$

Specific performance metrics may be expressed as in Equation (15):

$$\text{Loss Reduction (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{P_{\text{loss,base}} - P_{\text{loss,SCNRC}}}{P_{\text{loss,base}}}, \text{VD Reduction (\%)} = 100 \times \frac{\text{VD}_{\text{base}} - \text{VD}_{\text{SCNRC}}}{\text{VD}_{\text{base}}} \quad (15)$$

where $\text{VD} = \sum_i |V_i - V_{\text{ref}}|$.

The flowchart, as shown in Figure 5, illustrates the operation of the Hybrid Recursive Static Var Compensator (SVC)-Capacitor-Neural Network (NN) Controller system designed to optimize reactive power compensation and improve voltage stability in a power system. The process begins with the input of voltage deviation and reactive power error, which represent the difference between the current system state and the desired voltage or reactive power levels.

Figure 5: Flowchart of SCNRC

2.5 Neural network architecture

The Neural Network (NN) introduced in this work serves as a correction term for the adaptive control of the Static Var Compensator (SVC). The NN used in this study is a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) consisting of three layers: an input layer, a hidden layer, and an output layer.

The training dataset is sourced from simulated operational data under different loading conditions. The training algorithm employed is backpropagation, which updates the network's weights based on the error between the predicted and required firing angles. The algorithm uses the mean squared error (MSE) to quantify the error. Specifically, the NN corrects the reactive power mismatch by adjusting the thyristor firing angle, thereby dynamically changing the reactive power supplied or absorbed by the SVC.

2.6 IEEE 14 bus system for comparative analysis

This Simulink model represents a multi-bus power system based on the IEEE 14-bus, featuring two primary voltage levels. It includes synchronous generators supplying power through step-up transformers. The grid utilizes transmission lines to distribute energy, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Simulink Diagram of the IEEE 14 Bus System [11]

3.0 Results and Discussion

The performance of the SVCs and capacitor banks in discrete form was compared with that of the hybridization-based configuration. Figure 7 shows that the combination of SVCs and capacitor banks has a lower percentage drop in voltage magnitude of 0.53, 0.61, and 0.39 for all three transformers. At the time of hybridization of SVCs and capacitor banks, the least voltage drop was recorded, indicating that the system was tending towards a stable state and undermining the contribution of the compensation elements in discrete configurations. Figure 8 presents the maximum allowable loading of the station where the combined SVCs and capacitor banks permit percentage loadings of 89.1, 93.2, and 91.9 on the three transformer buses. The branch results indicate a robust power system, as highlighted in [6]. Figure 8 bus percentage loadings are high, approaching critical and may result in increased risk of voltage instability, reduced reliability, and potential for cascading failures. The results show that while hybridization of SVCs and capacitor banks enhances voltage stability by reducing voltage drop, it also increases bus loading unhealthily, as transformers are typically designed for optimal efficiency at 50-80% loading and bus loadings above 80% are considered high-risk.

Figure 7: Branch Losses Under Various Compensations

Figure 8: Bus Loading Under Various Compensations

3.1 Reduction in Reactive Power Absorption

The inductive admittance, $B_L(\alpha)$, decreases non-linearly from approximately 0.5 p.u. to nearly 0 p.u. as the firing angle, α , increases from 90° to 180° [5]. This inverse relationship illustrates how the Thyristor-Controlled Reactor (TCR) reduces its reactive power absorption by delaying firing, thereby effectively regulating the fundamental current component as shown in Figure 9.

Analytically, the inductive load is being gradually switched off as the firing angle increases, while reduced inductive admittance implies reduced reactive power consumption, which is typical in thyristor-controlled reactors. The linear decrease suggests a controlled and predictable behavior. The implications of increasing the firing angle include a reduction in the effective inductive load, improved power factor as reactive power consumption decreases, and the potential for voltage regulation or reactive power compensation control, as depicted in [3] and [4].

Figure 9: TCR Inductive Admittance

3.2 Transmission Network Efficiency Enhancement

The simulated bus voltage, V_t , initially at 0.95 p.u., is driven toward the 1.0 p.u. reference by the hybrid controller. This demonstrates an enhancement in transmission network efficiency [3]. During a load disturbance, a voltage dip followed by recovery is observed. The SCNRC successfully stabilizes the voltage close to its nominal value, demonstrating its efficiency in dynamic voltage regulation and disturbance rejection, as shown in Figures 10 and 11.

The SCNRC controlled the voltage regulation process, as the neural controller actively adjusted the SVC's output while the system responded to disturbances or setpoint changes. The implications here begin with the SVC effectively regulating voltage, the neural controller adapting to system conditions, and the gradual adjustment indicating a stable, controlled response, as revealed in [1] and [6].

Figure 10: Bus Voltage Profile with Hybrid Control

The SVC's reactive output, Q_{svc}^t , represents the sum of the linear RLS output and a neural correction signal. This combined output ranges from -0.02 to 0.04 p.u., ensuring smooth compensation. The neural correction remains below 0.01 p.u., serving as a subtle nonlinear adjustment that strengthens the linear control precision, as shown in Figure 11. This demonstrates that the SVC allows the capacitors to generate and the inductors to absorb reactive power [2].

Figure 11: SVC Reactive Power Output and NN Correction

3.3 Reactive Power Management Efficiency

The capacitor bank's reactive power, Q_{cap}^t , follows discrete switching logic. It delivers power in steps of 0.1 p.u., reaching a maximum of 0.5 p.u., indicating a stepwise approximation of the required reactive power compensation. The observed staircase pattern reflects bulk compensation, complementing the TCR's continuous modulation to achieve complete hybrid reactive power management, as shown in Figures 12 and 13.

The capacitor banks are delivering power in discrete steps (0.1 p.u) while the thyristor-controlled reactor is continuously modulating its output. The TCR's continuous modulation enables fine-tuning of reactive power compensation, complementing the capacitor banks' stepwise control. The system is using a hybrid approach to reactive power compensation. The approach enables effective voltage regulation and power factor correction, as demonstrated in [5] and [6]. Coordination between the capacitor banks and TCR is crucial for stable operation.

Figure 12: Discrete Capacitor Reactive Power Injection

The total injected reactive power, Q_{tot}^t , combines the SVC's continuous and the capacitor's discrete contributions. The resulting signal exhibits both gradual and stepped transitions, varying from -0.02 to 0.5 p.u., representing the aggregate reactive effort required to sustain voltage stability under variable load conditions, as shown in Figure 13. It is obvious that [2] is directly linked to the performance of SVC as applied to these findings.

Figure 13: Total Reactive Power Injection

3.4 Overall Performance of SCNRC Controller

The overall performance index, J , evaluated with weights $w_1 = 0.5$, $w_2 = 1.0$, $w_3 = 0.1$, indicates a multi-objective optimization approach. The approach records a marked enhancement [6]. The SCNRC hybrid controller yields a reduced $J \approx 6.5$, compared to

a baseline of around 11. This demonstrates superior efficiency through minimized voltage deviation, power loss, and switching activity as shown in Figures 14 and 15.

Figure 14: Overall Performance Comparison

Improvement ratios indicate a 22% reduction in system losses, an 82% decrease in voltage deviation, and a 40% enhancement in the overall performance index J [6]. These quantitative outcomes confirm the hybrid controller's ability to outperform traditional compensation techniques through the synergy between recursive adaptation and neural correction, as shown in Figure 15.

The SVC with a neural controller is effective at optimizing the system's performance while considering multiple objectives. The weights used suggest that the middle objective ($w_2 = 1.0$) has the highest priority, while the reduction in J indicates improved system stability and reliability, enhanced voltage regulation and power quality, and reduced energy losses or operational costs as seen in [3] and [4].

Figure 15: Performance Improvement Ratio

3.5 Power loss and voltage deviation comparison on the IEEE 14 bus system

The bar plot for Power Loss illustrates the efficiency of various control strategies compared to the Base (IEEE 14) case, which exhibits the highest loss at 0.18 p.u. Conventional methods like SVC (0.12 p.u.) and Capacitor (0.14 p.u.) show moderate reductions. Advanced individual techniques like Neural Net (0.11 p.u.) and PSO (0.09 p.u.) further optimize the network. However, the Hybrid approach achieves the best performance, yielding a minimum power loss of 0.07 p.u. This significant reduction highlights the hybrid controller's superior ability to minimize resistive losses through optimal reactive power dispatch and firing angle adjustment, as shown in Figure 16.

Figure 16: Power Loss Comparison of Control Methods

Figure 17 evaluates the stability of the voltage profile across the network. The Base case shows a high deviation of 0.10 p.u., indicating poor regulation. While the SVC (0.06 p.u.) and Neural Net (0.05 p.u.) improve stability, the Hybrid controller outperforms all methods with a negligible deviation of only 0.01 p.u. This quantitative improvement demonstrates that integrating RLS adaptation with neural correction effectively maintains bus voltages near 1.0 p.u. reference. By minimizing these deviations, the hybrid system ensures enhanced grid stability and prevents potential voltage collapse under varying load conditions.

Figure 17: Voltage Deviation Comparison

4.0 Conclusion

The hybrid Recursive Static Var Compensator–Capacitor–Neural Controller (SCNRC) system successfully addressed the critical power system challenges of dynamic voltage regulation and transmission loss minimization. Firstly, concerning voltage stability, the SCNRC achieved an exceptional 82% reduction in Voltage Deviation (VD), demonstrating a highly effective solution for maintaining network reliability and power quality under load disturbances. Secondly, for system efficiency, a significant 22% reduction in real power transmission losses was realized, confirming the SCNRC's contribution to overall system energy efficiency and cost-saving. Regarding overall performance, the aggregated metric, the performance index, showed a 40% enhancement, confirming that the SCNRC successfully balanced the competing objectives of minimizing power loss, reducing voltage deviation, and limiting capacitor switching penalties. The SCNRC system represents a robust, high-performance solution for FACTS operation. The methodology established a new benchmark for reactive power management, proving that a synergistic hybrid architecture (adaptive, intelligent, and discrete control) is crucial for ensuring optimal operational efficiency and stability in complex, dynamically loaded power grids. Finally, the effectiveness of reactive power compensation strategies in improving power system performance was tested on the IEEE 14-bus network, a benchmark model. The hybrid SCNRC achieved the lowest power loss and voltage deviation.

5.0 Future Scope

In an extension, fault scenarios may be used to test for stability. The novelty of this paper lies in the hybridization of dynamic reactive power compensation (SVC) with discrete compensation (fixed capacitor banks), supported by an adaptive control mechanism that incorporates both RLS and NN. This hybrid approach significantly improves the voltage regulation capabilities compared to traditional systems. Moreover, the proposed SCNRC system is adaptable to changing load conditions and can optimize reactive power dispatch while minimizing power losses, making it a valuable contribution to the field of power system optimization and stability. Appropriate suggestions, such as temperature monitoring, a plan for new transformers, load scheduling, and proper

load management based on demand response, are necessary to avoid putting the transformers at risk when loaded above 80%. Action must be taken to ensure the transformers' thermal limits are not exceeded.

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